

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH DELAY IN TUBERCULOSIS DIAGNOSIS IN NAMPULA, MOZAMBIQUE, 2017: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In Mozambique, 551 per 100,000 inhabitants have tuberculosis, and 58,000 are associated with HIV. This study estimated the mean delay in diagnosis and identified associated factors. **Methods:** descriptive, prospective, cross-sectional study with a quantitative approach, involving 366 patients with tuberculosis diagnosed and treated in eight health centres of the Nampula municipality. An interview script was used to collect demographic, social, and clinical information; the chi-square test and multinomial logistic regression were applied. **Results:** Most patients were male (54.9%), with a mean age of 34.6 years. The mean delay in diagnosis was 16.8 days, 95% CI (16.1 – 17.5), median of 14 days and interquartile (7.0 – 30.0). Factors associated with more than four weeks were: appointments at the *25 de Setembro* Health Centre (OR, 35.5; 95% CI, 1.9 – 649.7), appointments at the Nampula Psychiatric Hospital Health Centre (OR, 99.0; 95% CI, 3.5 - 282.4); distance greater than one hour or > 5km (OR, 2.5; 95% CI, 1.5 – 4.3); smoking (OR, 7.8; 95% CI, 12 – 29.8); patients who needed monetary assistance (OR, 4.2; 95% CI, 1.8 - 9.8); Clinical factors such as tiredness (OR, 3.5; 95% CI, 1.0 – 11.9), HIV co-infection (OR, 2.7; 95% CI, 1.1 – 6.8) and consulting a traditional healer (OR, 4.6; 95% CI, 1.1 - 18.5). **Conclusion:** To reduce patient delay in diagnosing tuberculosis, it is essential to improve the quality of access and medical care, support patients and consider HIV co-infection.

Keywords: Delay, diagnosis, associated factors, Tuberculosis, Nampula, Mozambique

Resumo

Introdução: Em Moçambique, 551 por 100.000 habitantes têm tuberculose, e 58.000 estão associados ao HIV. Este estudo estimou o atraso médio no diagnóstico e identificou fatores associados. **Métodos:** estudo descritivo, prospectivo, transversal com abordagem quantitativa, envolvendo 366 doentes com tuberculose diagnosticados e tratados em seis centros de saúde da cidade de Nampula. Um roteiro de entrevista foi usado para coletar informações demográficas, sociais e clínicas; foram aplicados o teste qui-quadrado e a regressão logística multinomial. **Resultados:** A maioria dos pacientes era do sexo masculino (54,9%), com idade média de 34,6 anos. O atraso médio no diagnóstico foi de 16,8 dias, IC 95% (16,1 – 17,5), mediana de 14 dias e interquartil (7,0 – 30,0). Os fatores associados a mais de quatro semanas foram: consultas no Centro de Saúde 25 de Setembro (OR, 35,5; IC 95%, 1,9 – 649,7), consulta no Anexo do Centro de Saúde da Clínica Psiquiátrica da Faina (OR, 99,0; IC 95%, 3,5 - 282,4); distância superior a uma hora ou > 5km (OR, 2,5; IC 95%, 1,5 – 4,3); tabagismo (OR, 7,8; IC 95%, 12 – 29,8); pacientes que precisavam de assistência monetária (OR, 4,2; IC 95%, 1,8 - 9,8). Fatores clínicos, cansaço (OR, 3,5; IC 95%, 1,0 – 11,9), coinfeção por HIV (OR, 2,7; IC 95%, 1,1 – 6,8) consultar um curandeiro tradicional (OR, 4,6; IC 95%, 1,1 - 18,5). **Conclusão:** Para reduzir o atraso do paciente no diagnóstico de tuberculose, é essencial melhorar a qualidade do acesso e assistência médica, apoiar os pacientes e considerar a coinfeção a HIV.

Palavras-chave: Atraso, diagnóstico, factores associados, Tuberculose, Nampula, Moçambique

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is an infectious and transmissible disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, usually affecting the lungs (pulmonary TB) but also other organs (extra pulmonary TB). Infection with *M. tuberculosis* results from the inhalation of infectious droplets produced by patients with Pulmonary Tuberculosis (PTB) or larynx when they cough, sneeze, speak or sing [1]. Some factors, such as the degree of infectivity (bacillary load), the type of TB, the period of exposure and environmental factors (closed and clusters) contribute to the increased risk of TB transmission[2].

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that new patients with PTB and extra pulmonary TB should receive a regimen for six months containing rifampicin (2HRZE/4HR), except for TB of the central nervous system, bone or joint, for which some expert groups suggest a longer therapy[3].

In addition, WHO recommends that national TB control programs ensure supervision and support for all infected patients, in order to reach the entire course of the therapy cycle, a procedure that should be accompanied with surveillance of resistance to medications, to monitor the impact of the treatment program and to plan standard regimens[3].

According to the WHO (2021), it is estimated that 10.6 million people fell ill with TB worldwide, of which, six million are men, 3.4 million women and 1.2 million children, in the same year, a total of 1.6 million people died (including 187,000 people with co-infection by the human immunodeficiency virus -HIV), representing the 13th leading cause of death and the second leading cause of infectious death after COVID-19 (above HIV and the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome -AIDS). However, an estimation of 74 million lives were saved through TB diagnosis and treatment between 2000 to 2021[4].

Within the African region (AFRO) of the WHO, Nigeria, South Africa, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania, and Mozambique are the most affected countries by TB[4].

According to the WHO 2022 Global Tuberculosis Report, the estimated incidence of TB in Mozambique in 2021 is 361 cases per 100,000 inhabitants (which corresponds to 116,000 cases of

TB in all clinical forms), associated with 29,000 cases of HIV positive and with 5700 cases of HIV+/TB deaths, clinical multidrug resistant MDR/RR-TB was estimated at 4,800 cases[4]. In 2021, 98,485 cases of TB of all clinical forms were reported, at a notification rate of 319 TB cases per 100,000 inhabitants, 30% were referred to by the community, however, most TB cases are in the economically productive age group, with a predominance of males (53%) and childhood TB representing 12% of all cases. According to WHO estimates, the National Health Service has not diagnosed 17,515 cases[5]. Previously, according to Chakaya, among the 10 million people affected by TB in 2019, about 2.9 million people (29%) went undiagnosed and untreated[6].

Definition of diagnostic Delay

Patient delay is the time between the onset of the first symptoms and the first medical appointment in the health system, and the system delay is the time between delivery of diagnosis and treatment to a patient from his first contact with the health system. In the context of Mozambique, the agricultural calendar and festive frame were used to facilitate the memory recall of patients[7].

A study performed in the city of Beira in 2013 with 622 patients, showed an average patient delay of 61 days (28–113) versus 62 days (37–120) for the healthcare system, with a total delay of 150 days (interquartile range, 91–240). Factors such as the practice of agriculture, first visiting a traditional healer when feeling the first symptoms, low knowledge of TB symptoms and the coexistence to a chronic disease, were associated with increased patient delay. More than two visits to health centre facilities, agriculture practice, and the coexistence of a chronic disease, have been associated with increased backlog of the health system[7].

The delay in the diagnosis of TB has been the subject of reflection and debate on the quality and opportunity of patients' access to health services, which may be linked to the delay of the patient and the delay of the health system in diagnosis and onset of treatment[8]. The delay in diagnosis and associated factors that affect TB cases make it an imminent danger of a permanent source of contamination within the community and a constant barrier to the control of the disease.

The objectives of this study were to: (i) describe participants' demographic, social and economic profiles, (ii) calculate the average time of delay in the diagnosis of TB and (iii) identify factors associated with TB diagnosis delay.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design: the study was descriptive and cross-sectional with a quantitative approach, conducted between September and October 2017.

Study site: The study was conducted in the Nampula municipality in eight (8) health facilities with TB patient care services: 1° de Maio Health Centre (HC), 25 de Setembro HC, Marrere General Hospital (HGM), Nampula Militar Hospital (HMN), Napipine HC, Nampula Psychiatric Hospital HC, Muhala Expansão HC and Namicopo HC. Nampula municipality is in Northern Mozambique with an estimated population of 760 214 inhabitants. (<https://www.ine.gov.mz/>).

Study population and selection criteria: the study population represents all patients diagnosed between January to December 2017 registered in the health centres records of Nampula municipality.

Inclusion criteria: all registered TB cases with at least two months of treatment and a maximum of six months, aged 18 years or older, and having resided in Nampula municipality for at least three months during the disease phase were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria: all patients with impaired physical or mental capacity, those who did not sign the consent form or those who abandoned before completing the interview were excluded from the study.

Variables:

a) Socio-demographic and clinical variables: gender, age, marital status, education, type, and place of residence; household, employment status, family income, clinical form of the disease, symptoms of the disease; TB/HIV/AIDS co-infection.

b) Care-seeking variable: first healing services sought by patient (traditional medicine services; health system services); time taken from onset of disease to seek healing service in days/weeks.

c) Lifestyle and behavioural variables: use of beverages; use of cigarettes; knowledge of TB before diagnosis.

d) Health service-related variables: category of professional who attended the patient (nurse, technician, physician); time spent in weeks/days for professionals to reach a definitive TB

diagnosis.

Source of data and measures: the sources consulted were the patients diagnosed by TB, clinical files, descriptive and inferential statistical measure were applied.

Data collection instrument: by means of standardized semi-structured interview form, the information on socio-demographic characteristics and income, clinical signs, course of consultation, habits and lifestyle of the patients were collected. The patients were identified in the registration book of the HC included after collecting the data, the interview was scheduled for each patient corresponding to their date of drug withdrawal. Eight (8) surveyors were trained in data collection instrument application and tested during the pilot study to assess the ability and validity of it. The data were entered into a database created in the statistical program SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science, version 22) to be processed and presented in tables in Microsoft Excel office version 10.

Sample size and sampling: In 2017, Nampula province detected 12,387 TB cases, of which about 7,660 cases were diagnosed in Nampula municipality[9]. The sample was determined according

to Marotti J. [10].
$$n = \frac{z^2 \times p \times (1-p) \times N}{D^2(N-1) + z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}, \quad (D = 5\%, z=1.96, p= 50\%, n=366)$$

The sample size was distributed according to the registration book in the eight HCs in proportion to consultation attendance and TB diagnosis (**Table 1**).

Sampling: after stratification and distribution of the sample per contribution of each HC, the patients were selected in a non-probabilistic manner, through voluntary participation (**Table 1**).

Statistical analysis: initially descriptive statistics of the sociodemographic, economic, and clinical profile were performed, post the mean, median of the delay time was calculated. The Chi-square test of independence to verify the association of demographic and clinical variables to time of delay in diagnosis, the data were presented in Cross Reference table in delay (15 days). Multinomial logistic regression model was used to check the influence of socio-demographic and clinical characteristics in odds ratio, Odds Ratio (OR) on delay time, critical significance level for rejection of null hypothesis ($p \leq 0.05$ at 95% CI was considered. SPSS was used for database and processing, Microsoft office Excel 2010 was used to prepare the tables of results.

Ethical considerations: The research was approved by the institutional committee of Bioethics for Health of the University Lúrio (CIBS_UniLúrio) with Ref.078/Augusto/CIBSUL/2017

(<https://rev.unilurio.ac.mz/cibs/>). All participants signed the informed consent form to manifest their voluntary participation, privacy and confidentiality were preserved and respected all standards of the declaration of Helsinki in its latest revision[11].

RESULTS

The results of this study are presented by objectives listed above.

1. Descriptive analysis of the study participants' profiles

a) Sociodemographic and economic of the study participants

Majority of the interviewed patients were 54.9% Male against 45.1% Female, age groups (25-34 and 35-44) were more frequent, Mean age was 34.6 years, Median 33 years and range (26.7- 42.0) in years, for marital status, 51.9% are married, 55.7% had only Secondary Education, the main residence was in the peri urban neighbourhoods (52.7%), the majority is religious and more than a third were Catholics (44.0%) and almost a third of the participants (32.0%) were interviewed at the 1° de Maio HC.

Regarding employability, more than half are unemployed, the monthly income of the majority was not evaluated, (71.0%) and only a quarter of the interviewees had a regular salary, however, an average of three people depend on this salary. In relation to distance travelled to the HC, most came less than 5km and did not employ any means of transport to commute. (**Table 2, 3**).

b) Descriptive analysis of TB symptoms in the participants

Regarding the symptomatology of the disease, most of the interviewees stated that they did not present fever, weight loss, lack of appetite, night sweats, tiredness, malaise, and chest pain, however, (79.8%) presented cough. When the symptoms started, most went to the health centre for consultation, only, (9%) consulted a traditional healer, and the time between the first consultation and the appearance of the first symptoms ranged from less than a week (8 days) to more than four (30 days). Nurses were the ones who attended the highest number, but unfortunately only (26.8%) cases were discovered in the first consultation and patients had three times of attempts on average, most of the diagnosed cases (91.3%) were pulmonary type, new cases (86.1%) and HIV Co-infection in (54.4%). Regarding the complementary exams performed, most of them did bacilloscopic and Hemogram (CBC), only (29.0%) had X-ray and three patients did

GeneXpert. The patients took three to six months of treatment, when asked the names of the drugs, most could not say the type of drugs ingested, declared they had received explanations from health professionals, and received their medication at the HC with good care.

c) Descriptive analysis of TB patient care in the health service setting in Nampula, Mozambique

The delay in TB diagnosis in the health system was described according to the number of visits the patient made to the HC before the diagnosis was confirmed. The average visit was 2.76 times, 95% CI (2.61 - 2.90) with a median of 3 visits, which determines the time to perform the consultation, CBC, Biochemistry, Rx, Bacilloscopic and GeneXpert if needed. Out of 366 patients interviewed, 28% (98) were informed of their diagnosis, 66% (243) unspecified diagnosis to the patient and 6% (25) attributed to other pathologies. Of those who were confirmed, most (99%) were in the first three visits and about half (55%) by the first visit in the HC. The cases of unspecified diagnosis, the nurses of 25 de Setembro HC attended 67% (157/243) of them. Among the patients attended at Nampula Psychiatric Hospital HC, one among them received his diagnosis after making ten consultations. The participants who answered the question about the attendance, 56% declared to be well attended, only six patients classified the facility-based care system as bad.

2. Mean time of delay in Tuberculosis diagnosis in the participants

The mean time to delay in diagnosis was 16.8 days, 95%CI (16.1 - 17.5), Median, 14 days, range (7.0 - 30.0). Patients admitted to the HCs of Namicopo, 25 de Setembro and Nampula Psychiatric Hospital, had the highest proportion of delay (>15 days) in diagnosis, the same delay was observed in patients in separation marital status (51.7%), and higher level of education (66.7%), practitioners of African traditional cult and Jehovah's Witness. The self-employed had also (64.2%), patients coming to the HC by bus (72.3%) and those who travelled more than 5 km distance to make the appointment (**Table 2,3**).

3. Factors associated with delayed Tuberculosis diagnosis in patients in Nampula municipality, Northern Mozambique

Bivariate analysis: significant association of delay time greater than four weeks, 15 days ($p < 0.001$). The set of variables such as age group (25-34), marital status single, not educated,

practicing religion, living in urban areas, being smoker and unemployed signalled significant association. However, gender ($p=0.76$) did not influence the delay in diagnosis of tuberculosis in Nampula municipality. (**Table 3**)

Multivariate Analysis by the Multinomial Logistic Regression Model

When it comes to association of factors with delay, some increased the delay of more than 4 weeks (>30 days), namely making an appointment at 25 de Setembro HC [OR, 35.5; 95%CI (1.9 - 649.7)], at Nampula Psychiatric Hospital HC [OR, 99.0; 95%CI (3.5 - 282.4)] and travel a distance greater than 5km to reach the HC. [OR, 2.5; 95%CI (1.5 - 4.3)], tobacco consumption [OR, 7.8; 95%CI (1.2 - 29.8)] and patients who needed monetary help [OR, 4.2; 95%CI (1.8 - 9.8)]. (**Table 4**).

The following clinical factors increased the likelihood of delaying TB diagnosis for more than four weeks (>30 days): presenting with fatigue [OR, 3.5; 95%CI, (1.0 - 11.9), $p=0.044$], being co-infected with HIV/AIDS [OR, 2.7; 95%CI, (1.1 - 6.8), $p=0.031$] and consulting the traditional healer when the first symptoms were felt [OR, 4.6; 95%CI, (1.1 - 18.5), $p=0.032$]. (**Table 5**)

DISCUSSION

To reduce the incidence of TB in Mozambique, early diagnosis and prompt initiation of treatment should be necessary. Analysis of factors associated with patient delay is an important step to identify how to improve the quality of TB care and control. This study evaluated the average time of delay and associated factors in TB diagnosis in Nampula municipality.

Most participants were male with low level of education, age between young and adults, due to the composition of the population of Nampula municipality, mostly young, the same characteristics were reported in some studies[12]–[14].

The mean time 16.8 days, 95%CI (16.1 - 17.5), and median 14 days, range (7.0 - 30.0) of delay in TB diagnosis in Nampula municipality, is considered acceptable for patient delay as indicated in some studies with 15 days mean delay [14]–[17]. Therefore, 34% of the patients interviewed had a delay time more than 15 days, this means that one third of the substantial proportion of TB patients in this municipality delay making the appointment therefore, continued to serve as a reservoir of infection and maintained the chain of transmission of the disease in the community

until diagnosis and treatment, which may have increased the burden of TB. The findings of this study show less days of delay than observed in other studies conducted, in Ghana in 2015 by Eric Osei and his collaborators where they found in 73 patients with median delay at 59 days (IQR, 5 - 123)[16], furthermore Getnet observed between 4 -199 days (range 15 - 50) [18], Saifodine in Beira city, centre region of Mozambique, 61 days (28 – 113) [7], Trigueiro, 20 days median time[8] and with Wysocki's result, it was similar to 15 days patient delay time[15].

Regarding the associated factors, the place of consultation played an important case in point, as presented at the HCs of 25 de Setembro and Nampula Psychiatric Hospital, showed association to the delay greater than 30 days in the diagnosis of TB for patients seeking health services in those HCs. This can be explained, on the one hand, by the fact that both are in the peri-urban area, on National Road N1, Nampula City's Labour Avenue, with easy access to public transport, but also with a high population density, surrounded by other services such as banks, ATMs, and shopping sites.

On the other hand, the quality of care, where the largest case of unspecified diagnosis is found in both centres. The HGM is considered a reference centre for the treatment of TB, but unfortunately the access route is impractical, with irregular public transport flow, distant from the city and with slight population density, characterized by the middle-income class and lack of other attractive factors for instance shopping. Analysing the distance travelled by patients more than 5km to seek health care, almost, 67.2% delayed in consultation more than 4 weeks (>30 days), this result was similar to some studies[14], [15], [19].

For behavioural habit of psychotropic substances consumption, alcohol did not mark difference in delay, a fact confirmed in a study in São Paulo[20], but the consumption of cigarette by the patient increased the delay to 7.8 times compared to non-smoker. The consumption of psychotropic substances is due to desperation in the cultural context, aiming to forget the day-to-day problems, consequently, the consumer by doing so neglects his/hers commitments, thus, postpones his/hers appointment at the beginning of the disease.

The patients need for financial support increased the delay to 4.2 times for 4 weeks (30 days) compared to those having the money, this result corroborates with the study conducted in Uganda

by Esther Buregyeya[21]. Also unemployment was significantly associated as in the study done by Muttamba[22].

Signs and symptoms such as cough and malaise did not interfere much in the delay of diagnosis, contrary to the symptom such as fatigue and HIV/ AIDS co-infection, which increased the delay by more than four weeks (>30 days) to 3.5 times and 2.7 times respectively. By its nature, fatigue accompanies co-infection, and is the initial state of disability, in which the patient will be immobilized in bed unable to perform his/her daily activities.

The first consultation at a traditional healer increased the delay by 4.6 times for more than 4 weeks (30 days) compared to the consultation done at the hospital at the onset of the disease, the fact was reported by other authors as consultation at the informal care provider, case in Uganda[18], [21], TB co-infection with HIV/AIDS increased by 2.7 times for more than 4 weeks (30 days), similar to reported by Saifodine in 2013 in Beira city [7].

CONCLUSIONS

This study revealed reasonable delay time compared to most observed studies; therefore, to reduce patient delay, it is imperative to strengthen and empower health workers with rapid and effective TB diagnosis tools, improve care by demanding patient information about their diagnosis, counsel patient's family members to provide support when needed, involve traditional medicine practitioners and health activists for rapid detection of new case in the community. But also eliminate the consumption of psychotropic drugs, provide transport support to those in need to reduce walking time and consider the co-infection of TB and HIV. The outcome of this study will allow provincial health policy makers to improve the TB control strategy in Nampula municipality.

What is already known about this topic?

1. There is a delay in patient care at health centre in Nampula, without evidence.
2. hypothetical factors for delay in the diagnosis of tuberculosis due to lack of transport and consultation with a traditional healer.

What this study adds

1. Time delay in days in diagnosing tuberculosis in health centres in the city of Nampula, Mozambique
2. The health centres where there is the greatest delay in diagnosing tuberculosis in the city of Nampula, Mozambique

Competing interests

This research has not received specific financial support from any funding agency in the public, commercial or non-profit sectors. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest related to the research.

Authors' contributions

Conception, study design and data collection: Fernando Mitano. Analysis, interpretation of data and writing of the manuscript: Abdoulaye Marega. Critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content: Fernando Mitano, Abdoulaye Marega and Jaibo Rassul Mucufu. Translation and revision of the version of the manuscript to be published: Abdoulaye Marega and Jaibo Rassul Mucufu. All authors read and agreed with the final manuscript.

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Tables

Table 1: Sample size distribution and stratification

Table 1 – TB diagnosis delay cases by demographic and social variables

Table 2–Distribution of cases of delayed diagnosis of TB in the municipality of Nampula according to socioeconomic characteristics

Table 3: Multinomial logistic regression to verify odds probability (OR) of demographic and social characteristics influencing delay in the diagnosis of tuberculosis, Municipality of Nampula, Mozambique.

Table 4: Multinomial logistic regression for factors associated with time delay in tuberculosis diagnosis, Municipality of Nampula, Mozambique

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Table 1: Sample size distribution

Health Centres	Total cases (2017)	%	Sample Size
25 de Setembro	1005	0,13	48
Napipine	251	0,03	12
1º de Maio	2449	0,32	117
Nampula Psychiatric Hospital	377	0,05	18
Muhala Expansão	921	0,12	44
Namicopo	753	0,10	36
HGM	1360	0,18	65
HMN	544	0,07	26
Total	7660	1,00	366

Table 1 – TB diagnosis delay cases by demographic and social variables

Demographic characteristics	Total (N=366)		Delay in TB diagnoses				P-value
	N	%	> 15 Days (n=125)		<15 Days (n=241)		
			n	%	n	%	
Health Centres							
25 de Setembro HC	48	13.1	31	64.6	17	35.4	<0.001*
Napipine HC	12	3.3	3	25.0	9	75	
1º de Maio HC	117	32.0	12	10.3	105	89.7	
Nampula Psychiatric Hospital HC	18	4.9	10	55.6	8	44.4	
Muhala Expansão HC	44	12.0	20	45.5	24	54.5	
Namicopo HC	36	9.8	27	75.0	9	25.0	
Marrere General Hospital	65	17.8	19	29.2	46	70.8	
Nampula Military Hospital	26	7.1	3	11.5	23	88.5	
Gender							
Female	165	45.1	55	33.3	110	66.7	0.76
Male	201	54.9	70	34.8	131	65.2	
Age group							
5 a 14	8	2.2	1	12.5	7	87.5	
15 a 24	67	18.3	22	32.8	45	67.2	
25 a 34	118	32.2	35	29.7	83	70.3	<0.001*
35 a 44	101	27.6	38	37.6	63	62.4	
45 a 54	50	13.7	21	42.0	29	58.0	
55 a 64	17	4.6	6	35.3	11	64.7	
65 and more	5	1.4	2	40.0	3	60.0	
Marital status							
Not married	176	48.1	60	34.1	116	65.9	<0.001*
Married/ <i>de facto</i>	190	51.9	65	34.2	125	65.8	
Educational Level							
No studies	50	13.7	16	32.0	34	68.0	<0.001*
Primary school	99	27.0	26	26.3	73	73.7	
Secondary school	204	55.7	77	37.7	127	62.3	
University	13	3.6	6	46.2	7	53.8	
Residence							

Urban area	173	47.3	42	24.3	131	75.7	<0.001*
Outskirts	193	52.7	83	43	110	57	

*Statistically significant. (TB)-Tuberculosis

Table 2–Distribution of cases of delayed diagnosis of TB in the municipality of Nampula according to socioeconomic characteristics

Socioeconomic variables	Total (N=366)		Delay in TB diagnoses				<i>p-value</i>
	N	%	> 15 Days (n=125)		<15 Days (n=241)		
			n	%	n	%	
Confess a religion?							
Yes	335	91.5	109	32.5	226	67.5	<0.001*
No	31	8.5	16	51.6	15	48.4	
Smoked tobacco or cigarettes before getting sick							
Yes	140	38.3	37	26.4	103	73.6	0.01*
No	226	61.7	88	38.9	138	61.1	
Before getting sick I drank alcohol							
Yes	176	48.1	62	35.2	114	64.8	0.17
No	190	51.9	63	33.2	127	66.8	
Before getting sick I used some drug							
Yes	4	1.1	3	75.0	1	25.0	0.08
No	362	98.9	122	33.7	240	66.3	
Current situation							
Unemployed	204	55.7	53	26.0	151	74.0	<0.001*
Employed	95	26.0	29	30.5	66	69.5	
autonomous	67	18.3	43	64.2	24	35.8	
Monthly income							
with salary	313	85.5	107	34.2	206	65.8	<0.001*
no salary	53	14.5	18	34.0	35	66.0	
Use of means to go to the Health Unit							
Yes	105	28.7	49	46.7	56	53.3	<0.001*
No	261	71.3	76	29.1	185	70.9	
Distance between the Health Unit and the place where you live							
<5km	247	67.5	45	18.2	202	81.8	<0.001*
>5km	119	32.5	80	67.2	39	32.8	

*Statistically significant. (TB)-Tuberculosis

Table 3: Multinomial logistic regression to verify odds probability (OR) of demographic and social characteristics influencing delay in the diagnosis of tuberculosis, Municipality of Nampula, Mozambique.

Associated demographic and social factors	Coefficient β	<i>p value</i>	Exp(β)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(β)	
				Min	Max
Delay time (1 to 2 weeks)					
Intercept	19.28	0.997			
25 de Setembro HC	2.63	0.020	13.9	1.5	127.4

1º de Maio HC	2.10	0.003	8.2	2.0	32.9
Nampula Psychiatric Hospital Annex HC	2.85	0.034	17.3	1.2	241.9
Marrere General Hospital	2.28	0.007	9.8	1.9	50.9
Nampula Military Hospital	0 ^b				
Urban area	1.11	0.037	3.0	1.1	8.6
Countryside	0 ^b				
Means you use to go to the Health Unit					
On foot	1.68	0.042	5.4	1.1	27.4
Motorbike	0 ^b				
Smoker	1.42	0.006	4.1	1.5	11.4
Non-smoking	0 ^b				
Delay time (3 to 4 weeks)					
Intercept	-6.18	0.999			
25 de Setembro HC	4.91	0.038	135.7	1.3	14076.1
Namicopo HC	5.83	0.018	340.5	2.7	42480.5
Nampula Military Hospital	0 ^b				
Means you use to go to the Health Unit					
Bus	4.04	0.021	56.9	1.9	1747.3
Delay time (more than 4 weeks)					
Intercept	37.33	0.992			
Time taken from home to the Health Unit (>60 minutes)	0.93	0.001	2.5	1.5	4.3
25 de Setembro HC	3.57	0.016	35.5	1.9	649.7
Nampula Psychiatric Hospital Annex HC	4.59	0.007	99.0	3.5	2821.4
Nampula Military Hospital	0 ^b				
Smoker	2.05	0.003	7.8	2.0	29.8
Non-smoking	0 ^b				
Needed monetary help to come to treat tuberculosis					
Yes	1.425	0.001	4.2	1.8	9.8
No	0 ^b				

(OR) – odds ratio. 0^b – reference

Table 4: Multinomial logistic regression for factors associated with time delay in tuberculosis diagnosis, Municipality of Nampula, Mozambique

Associated symptoms	Coefficient β	<i>P</i> value	Exp(β)	95% Confidence Interval of Exp(β)	
				Min	Max
Delay time (1 to 2 weeks)					
Intercept	-0.83	0.089			
Discomfort = Yes	2.50	0.021	12.2	1.5	102.1
Discomfort = No	0 ^b				
Cough = Yes	1.49	0.000	4.4	2.0	9.7
Cough = No	0 ^b				
Intercept	5.03	0.998			
HIV Co-infection = Yes	1.15	0.005	3.2	1.4	7.2

HIV Co-infection = No	0 ^b				
Delay time (more than 4 weeks)					
Intercept	-0.13	0.802			
tiredness = yes	1.26	0.044	3.5	1.0	11.9
Tiredness = No	0 ^b				
Where did you consult when you started having the first symptoms					
Traditional healer	1.53	0.032	4.6	1.1	18.5
Hospital	0 ^b				
HIV Co-infection = Yes	1.01	0.031	2.7	1.1	6.8
HIV Co-infection = No	0 ^b				

(OR) – odds ratio. 0^b – reference. VIH – human immunodeficiency virus infection